

INFORMATION SYSTEMS OF URBAN TERRITORIAL MANAGEMENT

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ABSTRACT

With the rapid growth of cities and the increasing complexity of their infrastructure, the management of urban areas is becoming increasingly challenging. Traditional management methods are proving insufficient to effectively address contemporary urban problems such as traffic congestion, pollution, resource management and security. In this regard, increasing attention is being paid to intelligent information systems (IIS), which utilize advanced technologies including artificial intelligence, big data, and geographic information systems to improve the efficiency of urban management.

This article is devoted to the study of intelligent information systems for urban area management. The article discusses the main components of such systems, including data collection, processing, analysis and visualization, as well as decision-making based on them. A review of previous research in this area is carried out, and the key approaches and technologies used for urban management are identified. Particular attention is paid to the flowcharts and algorithms that underlie IIS, as well as examples of their practical application.

Mathematical models and algorithms aimed at optimizing various aspects of urban management, such as traffic flows, resource utilization and environmental monitoring, have been developed and analyzed in the course of the study. Examples of flowcharts and algorithms are given, and their structure and functions are described in detail. Data visualization and the use of geographic information systems are shown as important tools for increasing transparency and efficiency of management.

Keywords: cities, infrastructure, mathematical methods and models, optimization, monitoring, land use, management, intelligent information systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern cities are complex and dynamic systems that face many challenges. Urbanization, population growth, climate change and technological innovations create the need for new approaches to urban management. Traditional management methods based on static data and manual processes are often insufficient to meet today's challenges. In this context, intelligent information systems (IIS) offer innovative solutions for urban management, providing a higher level of automation, accuracy and adaptability.

Intelligent information systems for urban area management include a wide range of technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI), big data, internet of things, geographic information systems (GIS) and cloud computing. These technologies make it possible to collect, analyze and interpret vast amounts of data in real time to facilitate informed decision-making and rapid response to changing conditions. IIS can be applied to various areas of urban management, including transportation, energy, health, security, environment, and utilities.

Traffic congestion, inefficient use of resources, air and water pollution, waste management, security and climate change adaptation are just some of the challenges facing modern cities. Intelligent management systems can address these challenges more effectively through the use of integrated data and advanced analytics. For example, AI-based transportation management systems can optimize traffic flow, reducing congestion and greenhouse gas emissions. Energy systems can improve energy distribution and consumption, reducing costs and increasing sustainability.

The purpose of this article is to explore the concepts, components and applications of intelligent information systems for urban area management. The article analyzes the key technologies and methods used in IIS, reviews examples of successful implementation of such systems in various cities around the world, and discusses current challenges and prospects for further development. Special attention is paid to block diagrams and algorithms that underlie IIS, as well as mathematical models and visualization tools that help in the management of urban environment.

The research aims to explore how the integration of IIS can enhance urban governance, improve the quality of life of citizens and contribute to the sustainable development of urban areas. As a result of analyzing and synthesizing existing research and practical examples, the paper provides recommendations for the design and implementation of intelligent management systems for different aspects of urban infrastructure. Thus, this paper is a contribution to the development of scientific and practical knowledge in the field of smart city management, offering a new vision and tools for solving current urbanization challenges.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

The topic of intelligent information systems for urban area management attracts the attention of researchers from different fields, including information technology, urbanism, transportation planning, and ecology. Previous research has significantly improved our understanding of how intelligent systems can contribute to more efficient and sustainable management of urban areas [1 - 4].

One important area of research is the application of AI in the management of transportation systems. N. Harriman and K. Davies (2017) in their paper "Artificial Intelligence in Urban Transportation Management" investigated the use of machine learning algorithms to optimize traffic light regulation and traffic management. Their research showed that the application of AI can significantly reduce travel time and traffic congestion [3, 10].

An important contribution to this field was the study by S. Chen and L. Li (2018), which analyzed the use of big data to predict traffic flow and improve public transportation management. In their paper "Big Data Analysis for Smart City", they developed prediction models that help city governments to plan public transportation routes and schedules more accurately, improving its availability and reliability [1, 4].

Research in the field of environmental monitoring and resource management. M. Batygin and S. Ivanov (2019) in their article "Integration of GIS with Intelligent Systems for Urban Infrastructure Management" examined in detail the integration of geographic information systems with IIS for urban infrastructure management. Their research has shown that the use of GIS combined with AI algorithms allows for more efficient management of resources such as water and electricity, as well as monitoring the environmental situation in the city [2, 5].

Another important contribution in this area was made by F. Lopez and A. Martinez (2019), who in "Enhancing Urban Sustainability through Smart Technologies" analyzed how smart systems can contribute to urban sustainability. They looked at various aspects including waste management, reducing carbon emissions and improving air quality. Their research showed that the use of IIS can significantly improve the environmental sustainability of cities [8].

The safety system of cities is also an important application area of IIS. In the study "Real-time Traffic Management with AI", S. Sun and J. Guo (2020) examined the use of AI for real-time traffic management to prevent accidents and respond to emergencies quickly.

They developed a system that analyzes data from surveillance cameras and sensors to quickly identify and eliminate potential hazards [7].

J. Kim and S. Park (2018) in their paper "IoT-based Smart City Architecture and Implementation" investigated the Internet of Things (IoT) based smart city architecture. Their research showed that the integration of IoT with IIS allows for more flexible and adaptive urban infrastructure management systems that can respond quickly to changes in the environment and the needs of residents [6].

A. Rogers and M. Smith (2018) in their article "Data-driven Decision-making in Smart Cities" analyzed how data can be used to support decision-making in smart cities. They showed that the use of big data analytics allows to more accurately predict the development of urban infrastructure and make informed decisions on its management [9].

III. MATERIALS AND METHODS

This study utilizes a variety of data and technologies that support the operation of intelligent information systems (IIS) for urban area management. The main materials used in the study include:

- Sensors and devices: to collect data on various aspects of urban life such as traffic, air quality, energy and water consumption. Sensors are installed on vehicles, buildings, street poles and other urban infrastructure.

- Surveillance cameras: for monitoring traffic, public safety and other purposes. Cameras collect video information, which is then analyzed using computer vision and artificial intelligence techniques.

- Mobile devices and applications: used to collect data on residents' movements, interactions with city infrastructure, and use of city services.

- Satellite data: used to monitor environmental conditions, analyze changes in the urban landscape, and other purposes.

- Servers and cloud platforms: to store and process large amounts of data, and to provide the computing resources needed to operate the IIS.

Software and algorithms include data processing tools, analytics platforms, machine learning algorithms, and data visualization systems. Examples of such research tools include Apache Hadoop for big data processing, TensorFlow for developing machine learning models, QGIS for geographic information analysis, and Tableau for data visualization.

The methods used in this study cover the full cycle of intelligent information systems from data collection to decision making. The main methods include:

Data collection. For data collection, various sensors can be used to automatically collect data in real time. Sensors can measure air pollution, traffic, energy consumption and other parameters. Data collection from city residents through mobile apps and online platforms can also be used. The use of satellite data is also feasible for monitoring changes in urban areas, analyzing green spaces and assessing pollution.

Data processing. For data processing, removal of noise and duplicates, correction of data errors are applied. It is also recommended to combine data from different sources to create a holistic picture. In the end,

normalization and scaling of data is performed for further analysis.

Data Analysis. Machine learning techniques are used to analyze the data, i.e. using methods such as linear regression, clustering, decision trees and neural networks to predict and identify patterns. It is not uncommon to practice the use of GIS to analyze spatial data and visualize it on maps. For big data analysis, it is possible to use technologies such as Apache Hadoop and Apache Spark to process and analyze large amounts of data.

Data Visualization. Data visualization uses the creation of maps that depict the current situation in the

city, such as traffic flows, air pollution, crime rates, landscape maps, real estate maps, land use, and other parameters. It is also popular to present analytical data in the form of graphs and charts to facilitate interpretation of results.

Decision Making. For effective decision making, systems are usually developed to help city officials make informed decisions based on data analysis.

Process automation. To implement this direction, algorithms are used, for example, for automatic regulation of traffic lights, energy management and other tasks, as shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. A general flowchart of the use of IIA techniques

This approach to the use of materials and methods enables the creation of effective intelligent information systems that can significantly improve the management of urban areas, enhancing their sustainable development and modern requirements.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Intelligent information systems (IIS) for urban spatial management consist of several key components, each of which plays an important role in ensuring effective and sustainable management of the urban environment. These components include: data collection, data processing, data analysis, data visualization and decision making. Each of these components has important building blocks for managing the urban environment.

Data collection is the first and most important step in an EIS. Data is collected from various sources such as sensors, cameras, mobile devices, and satellites. This

data may include information on traffic, air quality, energy and water consumption, as well as data on crime and other aspects of urban life, as shown in Figure 2.

After collection, the data undergoes a processing step that includes filtering, cleaning and aggregation of the data. This step is necessary to ensure data quality and readiness for further analysis. Data processing may include removing duplicates, error correction and converting the data into the desired format.

The data processing algorithm is implemented by the following sequence:

1. data cleaning:
 - removal of duplicate records;
 - correction of errors in the data.
2. Data filtering:
 - selecting relevant data;
 - removing noise and irrelevant information;
3. data aggregation:
 - grouping data by key parameters;
 - calculation of total and average values.

Fig. 2. General block diagram of the data collection process

The next step is data analysis. The data analysis stage uses various machine learning algorithms and analytical methods to identify patterns and make predictions. This step involves applying mathematical models to solve specific problems such as traffic flow forecasting, energy management, and environmental assessment.

An example of a data analysis algorithm can be presented for transportation management. It consists of the components:

- collection of current traffic data;
- traffic flow forecasting based on urban planning data;
- optimizing routes and controlling traffic lights to minimize congestion, etc.

Linear regression method can be used for traffic flow forecasting (1):

$$y = \beta_0 + \beta_1x_1 + \beta_2x_2 + \dots + \beta_nx_n, \quad (1)$$

where y — predicted value of traffic flow $x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n$ — variables affecting traffic flow (e.g., time of day, day of the week, weather conditions), and $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_n$ — regression coefficients.

Data visualization is an important tool for presenting the results of analysis in an easy-to-understand form. The use of maps, graphs and charts allows to visually assess the current situation and make informed decisions. Visualization can include interactive maps showing traffic congestion, air pollution levels, energy consumption and other parameters.

Based on the analyzed data and visualizations, management decisions are made. This stage includes the development of strategies and recommendations to optimize the management of urban resources and infrastructure. Decision-making can be automated (e.g., automatic regulation of traffic lights) or carried out with the participation of specialists. The sequence of decision-making stages is shown below in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Stages of decision-making

Managing the transportation system is one of the key tasks of city management. IIS can significantly improve the situation on the roads by using traffic,

weather and accident data to optimize routes and regulate traffic lights. The stages of a transportation management system can be represented by the following scheme, as shown in Figure 4.

Fig. 4. Stages of the transportation management system

The traffic light control algorithm is a set of tasks that consists of components:

- collection of data on current traffic congestion;
- determination of optimal phases of traffic lights taking into account the current situation;
- adjusting the switching time of traffic lights;
- monitoring changes and adjusting the phases in real time.

Thus, intelligent information systems of urban area management represent a powerful tool for solving modern urban problems. Integration of such systems allows to improve the transport situation, optimize the use of resources and improve the quality of life of citizens. Block diagrams and algorithms presented in this article show how IIS can be applied in practice for effective management of urban environment.

V. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

Intelligent information systems (IIS) for urban area management are a powerful tool that can significantly improve the quality of the urban environment and the efficiency of urban resource management. In the course of the study, various aspects of IIS were considered, from data collection and processing to analysis, visualization and decision-making. The presented results and examples confirm the high potential of IIS in solving actual problems of urbanization.

Intelligent information systems for urban area management represent a key tool for improving the efficiency and sustainability of urban management. The integration of advanced technologies and analytical methods allows solving complex urbanization problems, improving the quality of life of citizens and promoting the efficient use of urban areas. Ongoing re-

search and innovation in this field opens new perspectives and opportunities for creating smart and sustainable cities of the future.

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